

Collaboration Category Normalised Citation Impact (Collab CNCI): Evaluating Research in an Increasingly Collaborative World

AUTHORS SECTION

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ABSTRACT

Academic research has become increasingly internationally collaborative. While collaboration is generally viewed positively, ever lengthening author lists complicate equitably assigning credit to researchers etc. and therefore suitably evaluating research impact. Here, a new variant of Category Normalised Citation Impact (CNCI) which explicitly considers collaboration - Collaboration CNCI – is compared to the standard and fractional CNCI approaches. Using Web of Science data covering 2009 to 2018, results demonstrate that collaboration and fractional CNCI values are lower than the standard approach values but broadly similar despite differing methodologies, though differences exist (e.g., China). Analysis at the collaboration level (e.g., domestic vs international) provides insights into research output that would otherwise remain hidden. For example, CNCI values being driven by highly multi-lateral papers rather than domestic output (e.g., Sri Lanka). Such insights are crucial for research managers to thoroughly understand research performance and make better informed policy decisions.

KEYWORDS

Collaboration; CNCI; Research evaluation; Research impact; Policy

INTRODUCTION

Academic research has become increasingly internationally collaborative since the 1980s (Narin et al., 1991; Adams, 2013) and continues to do so. Reasons for collaboration are numerous and include technology and expertise transfer, as well as improved communication channels (i.e., cheap and accessible internet). Collaboration is generally viewed positively (Hicks and Katz, 1996); however, international collaboration has created issues concerning research evaluation - how should credit be assigned to authors, institutions, and countries on multi-author, multi-lateral papers, especially as increased collaboration leads to increased citation impact (Adams et al., 2019)? A common indicator used in research evaluation (Jappe, 2020) is Category Normalised Citation Impact (CNCI), which normalises citation counts by publication year, document type (e.g., article), and Web of Science subject category (one of 254 categories ranging from acoustics to zoology). Numerous variations of CNCI have been suggested to account for credit and collaboration (Gauffriau, 2021), but no consensus has been reached on the most suitable. Here, a variation of CNCI which explicitly considers collaboration, Collaboration (Collab) CNCI (Potter et al., 2020, 2022) is compared to the standard and fractional CNCI variants to demonstrate its strengths and utility in research evaluation.

METHODS

A dataset was constructed using Web of Science data from 2009-2018 inclusive. Only documents of the type 'article' were considered as these represent original research. Analysis was carried out at the country level using author metadata. Collab CNCI was calculated by normalising citation counts by publication year, document type and subject category (as with the standard CNCI method) but also involved an additional normalisation by collaboration type. These types consisted of domestic single institutional, domestic multi-institutional, international bilateral, trilateral and quadrilateral plus (i.e., four or more countries) output. No fractionalisation of credit took place. Fractional CNCI was calculated using the method of Waltman and van Eck (2015) using the fractional count of deduplicated entities multiplied by the CNCI value.

RESULTS

Figure 1 compares calculations for the three CNCI variants for three example research economies based on the size and maturity of their research base: large and well-established (Australia), large and newly established (China Mainland, which includes Hong Kong and Macau but is henceforth referred to as just China), and small and developing (Sri Lanka). Generally, collaboration and fractional CNCI values produce similar values, despite their very different methodologies. Both values are typically much lower than the standard CNCI value, though exceptions are present, particularly China where Collab CNCI matches standard CNCI. By the standard CNCI measure, Sri Lanka outperforms Australia and China for several of the years analysed but values are more erratic. When using collaboration or fractional CNCI, Sri Lanka does not outperform its peers in any year.

Due to the way Collab CNCI is calculated, analysis at the collaboration type level can be done. Figure 2 illustrates the distribution of citations, CNCI, and articles for China and Sri Lanka by the five collaboration types. China's research is heavily domestic (~76%), while Sri Lanka's is heavily internationally collaborative (~62%). China's domestic research accounts for ~64% of all its citations, whereas only 11% of Sri Lanka's citations come from its domestic articles (~38% share). Sri Lanka's citations mainly come from its most internationally collaborative work (~60% from international quadrilateral plus articles which account for only ~16% of articles). The CNCI boxplot (top left) elaborates this as Sri Lanka's international quadrilateral plus CNCI (white box on boxplot) far exceeds that of China (~8 vs ~2), while its values for all other types are below China's.

Figure 1. Standard, collaboration (Collab) and Fractional CNCI values for three countries (chosen based on the size and maturity of their research base) over a period of 10 years. A value of one represents world average.

Figure 2. Article and citation data (2009-2018) for two countries deconstructed by collaboration type (dom:single – domestic single institutional; dom:multi – domestic multi-institutional, int:bilat - international bilateral; int:trilat – international trilateral; int:quad+ – international quadrilateral plus). White squares on boxplots represent the mean, the vertical black line within the boxes the median. Note the use of log and differing scales.

DISCUSSION

The similarity of collaboration and fractional CNCI values suggests these methods may be interchangeable. However, credit fractionation, though straightforward, is likely to become increasingly abstract as author numbers increase to the tens and even hundreds and is also arbitrary (e.g., do all authors on a ten-author paper deserve one tenth of the credit?). Though international quadrilateral plus articles account for a small percentage of the entire dataset analysed (~4%) they clearly drive the citations for many countries, with Sri Lanka shown as the example here. Sri Lanka's standard CNCI performance, given its variance and the country's research capacity, could be anomalous (when comparing to China Mainland and Australia), resulting in ill-informed policy making. Collab CNCI and its deconstruction by collaboration type provide information on the distribution of citations for Sri Lanka and its reliance on highly multilateral papers for these. Such insights would have remained hidden if data were not examined at this level.

China, unlike many other countries, appears immune to the type of CNCI indicator used with values similar to one another. Reasons for this may include China's unique citation patterns and practices, including Chinese authors preferentially citing other Chinese (e.g., Bakare and Lewison, 2017; Shehata and Al-Rubaish, 2019) and longer reference lists than world average (Stahlschmidt and Hinze, 2018). Figure 1 also shows that China's CNCI values steadily increase over the period; many other countries did not. China, unlike Sri Lanka and others, does not need to rely on highly multilateral articles to gain citations and boost its performance.

CONCLUSION

Collaboration CNCI offers a new approach for explicitly considering the increase of collaboration in academic research without arbitrarily assigning credit. The use of five collaboration types separating domestic from international research also allows greater analysis of an entities' output. Such information is crucial for research and policy managers to better understand research performance and make better informed policy decisions.

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